

Power generation in photogalvanic cell composed of Toluidine Blue – Arabinose – NaLS system

K. R. Genwa* and Abhilasha Sonel

Department of Chemistry, Jai Narain Vyas University, Jodhpur-342 005, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : krg2004@rediffmail.com

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Abstract : In the present paper, the performance and conversion efficiency of the photogalvanic cell composed of Toluidine Blue – Arabinose in presence of anionic surfactant (NaLS) has been studied. It was observed that the cell generate power 48.78 μ W in short time and storage capacity has been obtained 123 min in dark. The effects of various factors like pH, concentration of dye, concentration of surfactant, diffusion length and electrode area on cell's power generation were also observed. A tentative mechanism has also been proposed.

Keywords : Photogalvanic cell, Toluidine Blue, Arabinose, storage capacity.

Introduction

The straightforward physical phenomenon of the nature – the sun light is the root behind the all life on the earth through the photosynthesis process of the plants. It is amazing that only about 0.03% of the sun light is utilized by photosynthesis. So, there is great opportunity before us to harness the power of this vital source of energy in favour of our energy demand of the nation.

A revolutionary phenomenon, discovered by Becquerel¹, which disclosed a new ways of obtaining electricity by direct conversion of solar energy, is known as photoelectrochemical effect, in which the irradiation of an electrode/electrolyte system produces a change in the electrode potential (on open circuit) or in the current flowing in the external circuit (under short circuit conditions)².

The photogalvanic effect was firstly reported by Rideal and Williams³ but Rabinowitch⁴ done remarkable work on the photogalvanic effect in well known iron-thionine system under different conditions, including variation of thionine and iron concentration and pH. Extensive work on the dye-reductant system was done many other investigators⁵⁻¹¹, sparked off interest of photochemists towards the further in this field.

Extensive work has been done successfully in this field using various dye-reductant systems in cell with good electrical output. But the grave disadvantage of the practical

application of the systems is rapid occurrence of back recombination's reaction which decreased the performance of photogalvanic cell. To enhance the cell performance, many workers used surfactant in cell solution and achieved encouraging results¹²⁻¹⁶.

Keeping these points in mind, we have chosen Toluidine Blue – Arabinose (Dye-reductant) system in present work with anionic surfactant NaLS in photogalvanic cell for solar energy conversion and studies in photogalvanic effect.

Results and discussion

Variation of potential and current with time :

First dark potential is noted by keeping cell assembly in dark chamber and then the cell is exposed to tungsten lamp (light source) and potential increased with time and reached up to a maximum stable value (V_{oc}). There was no effect of further illumination. Removal of light source decreased the potential. It may be due to occurrence of reversible photochemical reaction in cell solution only for some cycles.

It was also observed that maximum photocurrent produced by cell in short time. But it was noticed that there are decay in photocurrent with further illumination and we got a stable value of photocurrent (i_{sc}). It is represented graphically in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Variation of photocurrent with time.

Variation of photopotential and photocurrent with pH :

Effect of pH on cell photopotential and photocurrent was observed by using NaOH solution of different concentration. Photogalvanic cell containing Crystal violet-EDTA-DSS system was found to be quite sensitive to the pH of the solution. The electrical output of photogalvanic cell was affected by the variation in pH of the system. It was noticed that there is an increase in the photopotential and photocurrent of this system with increase pH in alkaline range. At pH 12.69 a maximum was obtained. There was a decrease in photopotential and photocurrent with further increase pH of the system. Results are summarized in Table 1.

pH	Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (μ A)	Power (μ W)
12.50	435.0	39.0	16.96
12.70	685.0	45.0	30.82
12.90	813.0	60.0	48.78
13.10	698.0	53.0	36.99
13.30	495.0	49.0	24.25

[Toluidine Blue] = 2×10^{-5} M; [Arabinose] = 2×10^{-3} M; [NaLS] = 5.6×10^{-3} ; Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ; Temp. = 303 K.

It was found that optimum electrical output obtained at particular pH value. It may be due to better availability of reductant's donor form at that pH value.

Effect of variation of dye concentration :

Experimental results with variation of dye concentration are given in Table 2. Results show that the system worked with efficiency at a particular maximum [dye] = 2×10^{-5} M.

Concn. of Toluidine Blue ($\times 10^{-5}$ M)	Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (μ A)	Power (μ W)
1.23	605.0	29.0	17.54
1.50	650.0	40.0	26.00
2.00	813.0	60.0	48.78
2.70	735.0	48.0	35.28
3.00	680.0	44.0	29.92
3.25	602.0	40.0	24.08

[Arabinose] = 2×10^{-3} M; [NaLS] = 5.6×10^{-3} ; pH = 12.90; Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ; Temp. = 303 K.

To increase or decrease the dye concentration from above mentioned value, cell's output decreased in both situations. At lower concentration of dye, there should be

low availability of dye molecules to excite and to donate electron to the platinum electrode. At higher concentration of dye, density of dye of molecules in path of platinum electrode should be large and therefore, they absorb major portion of light. Hence the dye molecules around the electrode will not be obtaining the desired light intensity.

Effect of variation of Sodium Lauryl Sulphate concentration :

The experimental results obtained by variation of NaLS concentration are given in Table 3.

Table 3. Effect of variation of NaLS concentration

Concn. of NaLS ($\times 10^{-3} M$)	Photopotential (mV)	Photocurrent (μA)	Power (μW)
4.8	436.0	36.0	15.69
5.0	693.0	44.0	30.49
5.6	813.0	60.0	48.78
7.2	700.0	53.0	37.10
8.8	488.0	40.0	19.52

[Toluidine Blue] = $2 \times 10^{-5} M$; [Arabinose] = $2 \times 10^{-3} M$; pH = 12.90; Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ; Temp. = 303 K.

The cell output increased with increase in [NaLS] but after a particular concentration, output of cell was decreased.

In absence of NaLS, decrease in electrical output was also observed. It indicates the presence of the charge transfer interaction between the dye-surfactant. The photo ejection of electron from dye-surfactant depends on the charge on micelle¹⁵.

Effect of diffusion length and electrode area :

The photogalvanic cell is prepared by immersing platinum foil electrode and saturated calomel electrode in two limb of cell solution container of H-shaped. The distance between these two electrodes called diffusion length. The cell's current parameter was studied with variation of diffusion length by using H-shaped container of different dimensions.

It was observed that maximum photocurrent (i_{max}) and rate of initial generation of current increased regularly with increase in diffusion length but equilibrium photocurrent remain unaffected. The results are reported in Table 4.

The current generation in cell was due to flow of electrode active species produced in cell reaction. If oxi-

Table 4. Effect of variation of diffusion length

Diffusion length D_L (mm)	Maximum photocurrent i_{max} (μA)	Equilibrium photocurrent i_{eq} (μA)	Rate of initial generation of current ($\mu A \text{ min}^{-1}$)
35	120	70	10.9
40	125	65	11.36
45	130	60	11.81
50	135	58	12.27
55	140	54	12.72

[Toluidine Blue] = $2 \times 10^{-5} M$; [Arabinose] = $2 \times 10^{-3} M$; [NaLS] = 5.6×10^{-3} ; pH = 12.90; Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ; Temp. = 303 K.

dized reductant (R^+) act as electrode active species in dark chamber, it will diffuse from illuminated chamber to the dark chamber to get electron from SCE. If this position is occurred, photocurrent must be decrease with increase in diffusion length. But it was not observed in our experiment. Therefore, we reach to at this conclusion that reduced Toluidine Blue and Toluidine Blue will act as electrode active species in illuminated and dark chambers respectively in support of experimental observations. However, reductant and oxidized reductant (R^+) can act as the electron carrier.

The cell's current generation was also studied with changing in area of platinum foil electrode. The effects of electrode area on maximum and minimum photocurrent are summarized in Table 5. With increasing electrode area, i_{max} was found to be increased but i_{eq} was decreased (negligibly small).

Table 5. Effect of variation of electrode area

Electrode area (cm^2)	Maximum photocurrent i_{max} (μA)	Equilibrium photocurrent i_{eq} (μA)
0.25	119.0	68.0
0.64	126.5	63.0
1.00	130.0	60.0
1.21	140.0	58.0
1.96	158.0	49.0

[Toluidine Blue] = $2 \times 10^{-5} M$; [Arabinose] = $2 \times 10^{-3} M$; [NaLS] = 5.6×10^{-3} ; pH = 12.90; Light intensity = 10.4 mW cm^{-2} ; Temp. = 303 K.

Current and power output characteristics, conversion efficiency and performance of the cell :

Open circuit voltage (V_{oc}) and short circuit current

(i_{sc}) of the cell were obtained by a digital pH meter (keeping the circuit open) and a microammeter (keeping the circuit close), respectively. The cell's i-V characteristic is shown between the current and potential values measured between the V_{oc} and i_{sc} by applying external load in microammeter circuit. i-V curve (Fig. 2) shows that it

is deviated from standard regular rectangular shapes (found in standard condition of 0 °C and 1000 W/m² insolation and in typical condition 25 °C and 800 W/m² insolation for solar cells). Power output characteristic of the cell is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2. Current-voltage (i-V) curve of the cell.

Fig. 3. Power-voltage curve of the cell.

A point in *i*-*V* curve at which product of current and potential was found to be maximum called the power point. Performance of the cell i.e. storage capacity^{17,18} denoted by $t_{1/2}$ was observed 123 min by keeping the cell at power point in dark and noted the time required in fall of power output to its half value (Fig. 4).

was found to increase in presence of surfactant NaLS with dye (Arabinose) in the cell solution. The photoejection of electron from dye-surfactant system suggesting the tunneling of photoejection from micellar phase to aqueous phase was observed by Alkaitis *et al.*¹⁹ whereas Bhowmik *et al.*²⁰ and Mukhopadhyaya and Bhowmik²¹ have ob-

Fig. 4. Performance of the cell.

The conversion efficiency and fill factor of the cell (with platinum foil electrode of 1 cm² electrode area) were determined 0.144% and 0.259 respectively by following formula :

$$\text{Conversion efficiency } (\eta) = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{A \times 10.4 \text{ mW/cm}^2} \times 100\% \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Fill Factor (Ff)} = \frac{V_{pp} \times i_{pp}}{V_{oc} \times i_{sc}} \quad (2)$$

where, V_{pp} and i_{pp} represent the values of potential and current at power point, respectively. V_{oc} and i_{sc} are the open circuit potential and closed circuit current and A is the area of platinum foil electrode.

Role of Arabinose and NaLS :

Arabinose acts as photosensitizer in the photogalvanic cell solution. It absorbs the light radiations and initiates the cell reaction. The detailed reaction mechanism is shown in mechanism section. The electrical output of the cell

served the photoinduced electron transfer between micelles and thionine dye through a charge transfer interaction. The photoejection of electron from dye-surfactant depends upon the charge on micelle. The negative potential present inside the aggregates on an anionic micelle (NaLS) will make ejection of electron easier and therefore, the efficiency of photogalvanic cell is increased.

Mechanism :

According to photochemistry of dyes in solution, chemically reactive species is the triplet state of the dye. Specifically, when certain dyes are excited by light in the presence of electron donating substances, the dyes are rapidly changed into colourless ("reduced") form. The dye is now a powerful reducing agent and will donate electrons to other substances, with the dye being returned to its oxidized state.

On the basis of above studies, a tentative mechanism has been proposed as follows :

Illuminated chamber :

(Ground state) (First excited state) (Triplet state)

At platinum electrode :

Dark chamber :

At SCE :

where Dye, Dye⁻, R and R⁺ represent the Toluidine Blue, reduced form of dye, reductant and oxidized form of reductant, respectively.

Experimental

Reagents and apparatus :

The dye Toluidine Blue, reductant Arabinose, surfactant Sodium Lauryl Sulphate and sodium hydroxide were LOBA, BDH, s.d. fine and Qualigen products, respectively. All solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Other necessary requirements of our experiment were a blackened H-shaped container, a platinum foil electrode of 1 cm² area, a saturated calomel electrode, a digital pH meter (Systronics model 335), a microammeter (INCO-65), 200 W tungsten lamp and a variable resistor.

Procedure :

Stock solution of dye (1 × 10⁻³ M), reductant (1 × 10⁻² M), surfactant (1 × 10⁻¹ M) and NaOH (1 N) were prepared in double distilled water. During preparation of dye solution the precaution taken to protect the solution from light and to store in darkened container.

The mixture of dye, reductant, surfactant and NaOH was made up to 25 ml and placed in the blackened H-shaped container. A platinum foil electrode (1 cm²) immersed in one limb of cell container which contain a transparent window and a SCE was in another one. When cell obtained stable dark potential value, platinum foil electrode was exposed to light. A water filter was used between light source and cell in cut-off thermal radiation. With the help of pH meter and microammeter, cell's electrical output - potential and current were measured respectively. The i-V characteristics of the cell were also

studied by applying external load in microammeter circuit with variable resistor.

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